

Innovative concepts and technologies for ECOLOGically sustainable NUTRIent management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air

Newsletter – Issue 6

April 2026

WELCOME

Welcome to the final edition of the Econutri Newsletter!

As the project reaches its final stage, we are proud to share the major results, achievements and impact activities that marked the last months of Econutri. From the creation of the Innovation Handbook (deliverable) and the completion of the Econutri Hackathon Series, to international visibility through CORDIS and strong partner activities across Europe and China, this final issue celebrates how Econutri has moved from research to practice.

Over 42 months, Econutri brought together a multidisciplinary EU-China consortium to develop, validate and demonstrate innovative solutions for sustainable nutrient management, pollution reduction, circular agriculture and climate-smart farming.

We invite you to explore the final highlights of the project and continue following the Econutri legacy through our website and online channels.

[Econutri website](#) [Econutri LinkedIn](#)

From Research to Practice

**ECONUTRI Innovation Handbook Presents 24 Solutions for
Sustainable Nutrient Management**

One of the key legacy outputs of Econutri is the "[ECONUTRI Innovation Handbook](#)", a final deliverable and a practical guide bringing together the innovative technologies developed, validated and demonstrated during the project.

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The Handbook presents 24 technologies addressing some of the most urgent challenges in modern agriculture:

- ✓ reducing nutrient losses
- ✓ improving nutrient-use efficiency
- ✓ recovering valuable resources from organic residues
- ✓ mitigating greenhouse-gas and ammonia emissions.

Covering the full agricultural nutrient cycle – from manure and biowaste processing to crop production, livestock systems, greenhouse cultivation, field application and digital decision-support tools – the Handbook translates Econutri’s scientific results into practical knowledge for farmers, advisors, researchers, industry actors and policymakers.

By bringing these results together in one accessible reference document, Econutri strengthens the **bridge between research and practice**. The Handbook supports the uptake of sustainable nutrient management solutions and contributes to the project’s long-term legacy: healthier soils, cleaner water, improved air quality and more resilient agricultural systems.

Stay tuned – the handbook will become publicly accessible after the end of the project and the completion of the final publication and dissemination procedures.

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Co-Creating Innovation with End Users

ECONUTRI Hackathon Series

4 Hackathons | 4 Countries | 1 Shared Mission

During its final phase, Econutri organized a series of four hackathons across Europe, bringing together researchers, students, growers, advisors and innovators to explore practical tools for **sustainable nutrient management**.

[AUA Hackathon – Athens, Greece](#)

15–16 December 2025

Focus: NUTRISSENSE DSS

The first hackathon introduced the NUTRISSENSE decision-support system, showing how digital tools and ion-selective electrodes can support smarter nutrient management and reduce environmental losses.

[UAL + Cajamar + COEXPHAL Hackathon – Spain](#)

10–11 February 2026

Focus: *Online fertigation tool for greenhouse crops*

The second hackathon showcased an innovative fertigation tool integrated into Cajamar’s Tierra platform, helping greenhouse growers improve irrigation and nutrient planning.

[WUR + LGNL Hackathon – Naaldwijk, The Netherlands](#)

13, 20 & 27 March 2026

Focus: *Virtual Lysimeter DSS*

The third hackathon focused on irrigation optimization in soil-bound horticulture, helping users reduce pollution risks through better water management.

[UNITO Hackathon – Italy](#)

13–14 April 2026

Focus: *Waste biomass valorisation & nutrient recovery*

The final hackathon explored circular solutions for transforming waste biomass into valuable resources, highlighting Econutri’s vision for nutrient recovery and circular agriculture.

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ECONUTRI in the EU Spotlight

CORDIS Project of the Month

We are proud to share that **Econutri** has been featured on the official **CORDIS** website, the European Commission's primary platform for showcasing EU-funded research results.

The CORDIS article, titled "**Novel tech for next-generation green agriculture**", highlighted **Econutri's** contribution to reducing fertilizer dependency, preventing nutrient pollution and supporting more resilient agricultural systems.

This EU-level recognition is a major communication achievement for the project and confirms the relevance of ECONUTRI's results for farmers, researchers, advisors, policymakers and the wider European agricultural community.

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From Innovation to Adoption:

Policy Pathways for Nutrient-Smart Agriculture

Econutri shows that innovation alone is not enough. To move sustainable nutrient management from **research to real adoption**, farmers need supportive policy frameworks, practical tools and targeted incentives.

Key recommendations include:

- ▣ **Reward low-emission practices** through subsidies and technical support for manure management, precision fertilization and nutrient recycling.
- ▣ **Support farmers in the transition** to circular and regenerative farming through training, advisory services and practical demonstrations.
- ▣ **Use monitoring and decision-support tools** to verify emission reductions and improve nutrient-use efficiency.
- ▣ **Promote farmer-led knowledge exchange** through demonstration farms, peer learning and regional training networks.

Econutri in the spotlight

During the final months of the project, between November 2025 and April 2026, **Econutri** partners actively participated in conferences, educational events, and field visits across Europe and China – showcasing innovative, nature-based nutrient solutions and inspiring agronomists, scientists, and innovators on how to reduce waste and emissions.

Highlights are listed below.

14 November 2025 – AUA

Econutri coordinator spoke on the program “Agricultural Development” on the online Greek channel T-PRESS WEB TV

[Watch the full interview](#)

25–27 November 2025 – INHORT

International Trade Fair of Food and Organic Products Bio Expo Warsaw, Poland

3 December 2025 – INHORT

Transformative Governance for Food Systems and Biodiversity", Copenhagen, Denmark

11 December 2025 – COEXPHAL & UAL

Almería Agroecology Living Lab Webinar

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13-16 January 2026 – InHort
visits partner Stanley –
Stanley Agricultural Group, China

23-28 January 2026 – UNITO & NIBIO visit CAU, HAAFS, STANLEY

Strengthening EU-China Long-Term Cooperation

- Workshops held in
 - a) Zhengzhou, Beijing hosted by CAU and
 - b) Shijiazhuang, hosted by HAAFS
- Sino-EU Conference on Agricultural Nutrient Management Based on Nature-Solutions, organised by HAAFS, CAU and Stanley Agriculture Group in Shijiazhuang, Hebei Province.

[Read more about the Joint Workshops](#)

February 2026 – COEXPAL & UAL
features ECONUTRI in AenVerde
magazine, Spain

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11 February 2026 – UNITO

welcomes more than 300 students from 21 local high schools during Radici Event– *Agricultural Education for a Sustainable Future*

10 March 2026 – ATB

students from Leibniz Gymnasium Potsdam visited ATB's ECONUTRI demonstration site at LVAT Groß Kreutz, Germany

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March 2026 – UTAD, NIBIO and CAU

Publish a Book to Advance Circular Agriculture

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**Clustering with Tallheda project
Digital Transformation in Agriculture**

1. 24-25 November 2025 – AUA

3rd Tallheda Brainstorming Action event

2. 1 April 2026 – AUA

Tallheda Workshop

Dissemination Continues Until the Final Days

1. [27 April 2026 AUA, Greece](#)

Open Day at the Agricultural University of Athens, visiting the greenhouse facilities with cucumbers.

2. [29 April 2026 ARI, Cyprus](#)

Econutri Final Event in Cyprus

(held after the publication of the last newsletter)

With dissemination activities planned until the final days, **Econutri** continues to strengthen its legacy and bring sustainable nutrient-management solutions closer to practice.

Econutri Partners

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